

THE EFFECT OF THE Z-TRACK TECHNIQUE ON PAIN AND DRUG LEAKAGE IN INTRAMUSCULAR INJECTION AT PEOPLES MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL NAWABSHAH; RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL (RCT)

Sania Rajput^{*1}, Abdul Haque², Pir Bux Jokhiyo³, Bakhtawar⁴, Ramsha⁵, Nasim⁶

^{*1,4,5,6}GBSN, College of Nursing Female Nawabshah, Affiliated Peoples University of Medical & Health Sciences for Women, Shaheed Benazirabad, Sindh, Pakistan

²Nursing Instructor, College of Nursing, Female, Peoples University of Medical & Health Sciences for Women, Shaheed Benazirabad, Sindh, Pakistan

³Associate Professor, Begum Bilqees Sultana Institute of Nursing, Peoples University of Medical & Health Sciences for Women, Shaheed Benazirabad, Sindh, Pakistan

¹rajputsania156@gmail.com, ²ahaquekhoso@yahoo.com, ⁴quershikinza49@gmail.com
⁵aliramsha582@gmail.com, ⁶nasimsahito3@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18831174>

Keywords

Z-Track Technique,
Intramuscular Injection, RCT,
Nursing Practice, Complications.

Article History

Received: 29 December 2025

Accepted: 14 February 2026

Published: 28 February 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Sania Rajput

Abstract

Background: Intramuscular (IM) injections are among the most common nursing procedures for administering medications such as pain, drug leakage, bruising, and hematoma. The Z-Track Technique (ZTT) is designed to minimize these adverse effects by displacing the skin laterally before injection to seal the medication within the muscle tissue.

Material & methodology. This study was Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) conducted at People Medical College Hospital Nawabshah, a total of 92 adult patient aged 18–60-year enrolled in this study. The total sample size of study was 92. Moreover, participants randomly assigned to either conventional IM group (n=46), and z track technique (n=46).

Results. The study revealed that baseline demographic character including age gender BMI and history of prior IM injection were comparable between group ($p > 0.05$). Pain scores were lower in the Z-Track group. Moreover, ZTT found significantly lower occurrence hematoma (25% vs 75%, $p < .001$) reduces bruising severity lower redness and minimal swelling compared conventional group.

Conclusion The Z track technique is an effective and safe method for IM injection. Significantly in less reporting for risk for drug leakage, bruising redness and swelling among patients compared to conventional technique.

Introduction:

Intramuscular injection are commonly performed by nurses medication administration directly into the muscles, include antibiotics, vaccines, pain killers and hormonal treatment.¹ Improper technique during intramuscular injections improper administration can lead to

complications including as bruising, muscles injury, infections, improper technique, tissue necrosis, with discomfort.^{2, 3} Furthermore, improper administration of intramuscular injection can lead to complications such as hematoma muscles contracture infection abscess

nerve injury tissue death and discomfort with discomfort being the most commonly reported.⁴ Intramuscular injections can be administered at several anatomical sites, including the ventrogluteal, deltoid, femoral, and patellofemoral areas, depending on the patient's muscle condition and medication volume.⁵ The nurse determines the injection site best on the patient body mass index the volume of medication muscles development and the proportion of muscle at the site.⁶ When intramuscular injections are performed using the correct technique, they are associated with reduced pain and fewer local complications.⁷ Moreover, in health care setting nurses play vital role in preparing and safely administering medication educating patient and their caregivers about the drug and monitoring patient response to treatments.⁸ This technique can cause discomfort fear and anxiety in children. Nurses use various technique to reduce pain during intramuscular injection such as skin tapping and cold application.⁹ Among these intervention the most effective are skin tapping applying pressure before the injection and rotating the injection site.¹⁰ Avoiding infiltration of the subcutaneous tissue, especially with irritant solutions, reduce pain, swelling, and inflammation at the injection site.¹¹ This contributes to a more comfortable experience for the patient.¹² Administering medication at a depth of at least 5 mm into the muscle maximizes its effectiveness.¹³ When combined with the correct needle length and gauge, proper injection site, relaxed muscle, and appropriate positioning, ZTT ensure the best therapeutic or immunogenic outcome.¹⁴ Improve injection stability.¹⁵ The non-dominant hand stretches the skin laterally while also stabilizing the syringe with the first and second fingers.¹⁶ This requires good manual dexterity and prevents needle movement, which could otherwise damage tissue.¹⁷ further, slow injections benefit particularly from this stability, reducing the negative effects of needle wiggling.¹⁸ The skill of the person administering the injection, along with the patient keeping the arm relaxed and immobile, further enhance accuracy and safety, contributing to the overall stability of the procedure.¹⁹

Material & Method

This study was a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) study design and was conducted from September to November 2025 at Peoples Medical College Hospital, Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan. Participants were selected using a random sampling technique from a total population of 250 individuals. The sample size was calculated using Rao software, with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, resulting in a final sample size of $n = 92$ for the experimental study. Participants were randomly assigned to either the experimental group as Z-track technique, and the control group (conventional intramuscular injection technique), with 46 participants allocated to each group.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Adult patients aged ≥ 18 years.
2. Patients prescribed intramuscular medication.
3. Patients who consent to participate.
4. Indoor Patients.
5. Both Genders.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with skin infections
2. Patients with bleeding disorders
3. Patients on analgesics or sedatives before the injection.
4. Patients allergic to the prescribed medication.
5. Out Door Patients.

Data Collection Tools:

The Data was collected after permission of Ethical Review Committee of College of Nursing, Female Nawabshah, Affiliated People University of Medical, and Health Sciences for Women, Nawabshah Shaheed Benazirabad, vide letter No, CON/PMCH/ GBSN/ 235. Following the inclusion criteria, data were collected after obtaining formal informed consent from each participant. The intramuscular was administered from senior nurse with more than ten years of experience following the proper techniques, and procedures. Moreover, injection site measured by senior nurses along with the researchers. Additionally, Pain Intensity: Measured using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) immediately after injection and after 30 minutes for Drug Leakage observed by checking for visible leakage of

medication at the injection site within five minutes post-injection. Furthermore, local Complications such as redness, bruising hematoma, and swelling at the injection site recorded after 24 hours.

Data Analysis: Data was analyzed using SPSS software, in descriptive statistics characteristic such as mean standard deviation frequency and

Results:

percentage. The demographic characteristic and measured to evaluate difference between the Experimental and control group in term of pain medication leakage and nurse satisfaction to analyze relationship between variable the independent t test and chi-square test was analyzed, and statistically measured ($p=.05$).

Table.No.01: Socio-Demographic Characteristic of Study Participant:

Socio demographic characteristics	Group I (conventional group) (n=46)		Group II (Z-track technique) (n=46)		P- value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Age categories					.585
30-35	17	36.9 %	21	45.7 %	
35-40	8	17.4%	8	17.4%	
40-45	11	23.9 %	11	23.9 %	
45-60	10	21.7%	6	13.0%	
Gender:					.136
Male	24	52.2%	31	67.4%	
Female	22	47.8%	15	32.6%	

Table.No.01: shows the socio demographic of study participant .no significant difference was found between conventional IM group & ZTT group regarding age ($p = 0.585$). similarly, no significant difference was found Between two

group the term of gender distribution ($p -.136$) these finding indicate both groups were comparable with respect to socio-demographic characteristics.

Table No.02: Comparison of Body Mass Index Between Conventional and Z Track Technique Groups:

	(conventional group) (n=46)	(Z-track technique) (n=46)	p_ value
BMI categories:	Frequency	Frequency	0.724
<18.5(underweight)	Percentage%	Percentage%	
18.5-24.9(normal)	16(34.8%)	12(26.1%)	
25-29.9(overweight)	21(45.7%)	25(54.3%)	
30-39.9(obese)	2(4.35%)	8(17.4%)	
	7(15.2%)	1(2.2%)	

Table No.02: compare the distribution of BMI, between the conventional injection group and z track technique group, the majority participant in both groups had normal BMI statistically analysis

there was no notable difference between two groups BMI ($p = . 0.724$)

Table No: 03. Clinical Health Data of Participants in Both Study Groups:

Pervious IM	(conventional group) (n=46)	(Z-track technique) (n=46)	p_ value
	Frequency Percentage (%)	Frequency Percentage (%)	
Pervious IM injection			
Yes	29(63%).	43(86%).	0.521
No	17(37%)	3(14 %)	
Medication administered			
Pain Killer	8(17.3%)	8(86.0 %)	0.924
Antibiotic	34(73.9%)	35(14.0 %)	
other	4(8.6%)	3(16.0 %)	

Table No: 03. shows the clinical health data of participant in both groups. Most participant in both groups had pervious IM injection (conventional: 63% ZTT 86%) and medication administered was similar between groups. No

significant statistically difference were found in pervious IM injection or medication type ($p = 0.521$ and $p = .924$) indicating comparable clinical health characteristics,

Table No. 04: Comparison of Injection Site Leakage And Medication Backflow Between Conventional Group and Z Track Technique:

Item	Studied group				p_ value
	(conventional group) (n=46)		(Z-track technique) (n=46)		
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
leakage injection site					
Yes	39	84.7%	8	17.1%	.001
No	7	15.2%	38	82.6%	
Medication backflow					
needle tract					
Yes	36	78.3%	7	78.3%	.001
No	10	21.7%	39	21.7%	

Table No.04: shows that injection site leakage was significantly higher in the conventional group (84.7%) compared to the ZTT group (16%) while medication backflow was also more frequent in the conventional group (78.3%) than in the ZTT group (14%) chi-square analysis indicating

difference are statistically significant ($p < .001$) demonstrating that the ZTT effectively reduce both injection site leakage medication backflow, confirming its superiority over the conventional IM injection.

Table No. 05: Comparison of Hematoma Occurrence Between Conventional Group and Z Track Technique:

Subject of hematoma		P_ value	
Conventional IM n (%)		Z-track technique n (%)	
None	13(27.10%)	35(72.90%)	.001
Developed	33(75.00%)	11(25.00%)	

Table No.05 The occurrence of hematoma was compared between group 1 and groups 11. in the conventional IM group hematoma was present 33 (75.0%) participant whereas in the z track technique group hematoma was observed 11(25.0 %) participant. Conversely absence of hematoma

was noted group 1. 13 (27.1%) and z track technique 35 (72.9%) participant group. The difference between two group was statistically significantly ($p < 0.001$) indicating z track technique significantly reduced occurrence of hematoma compared to the conventional IM injection

Table No.06 Comparison of Bruising Severity Between Conventional IM Injection And Z-Track Technique:

Subject of Bruising		Subject Of Bruising			
		None	Mild	Moderate	Sever
Conventional group	Frequency	4	22	18	2
	Percentage	8.7%	47.8%	39.1%	4.3%
Z-track technique group	Frequency	40	6	0	0
	Percentage	87.0%	13.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table No.06. In the conventional IM injection group bruising was absent 4 (8.7%) mild 22 (47.8%) moderate 18 (39.1%) sever 2 (4.3%)

participants. in the z track technique group .no bruising 40 (87.0%) mild 6(13.0%), and Sever 0((0.0%) participant respectively.

Table no. 07. Comparison of Redness Between Conventional IM Injection And Z-Track Technique:

Subject of Redness		Subject of Redness	
		None	Present
Conventional IM	Frequency	16	30
	Percentage	34.8%	65.2%
Z-track technique	Frequency	42	4
	Percentage	91.3%	8.7%

Table No. 07 In the conventional IM injection group 34.8% of participant did not develop redness at injection site, while 65.2% experience redness. in the z track technique group 91.3 of

participants had no redness and only 8.7% had redness. The indicate that the ZTT is associated with lower incidence of injection site redness compared with conventional method.

Table No. 08. Comparison Of Swelling Between Conventional And Z-Track Technique:

Subject of swelling		Subject Of Swelling			
		None	Mild	Moderate	Sever
Conventional IM	Frequency	12	17	15	2
	Percentage	26.1%	37.0%	32.6%	4.3%
Z-track technique	Frequency	38	8	0	0
	Percentage	82.6%	17.4%	0.0%	0.0%

Table No. 08. In the conventional IM injection group swelling was absent 12 (26.1%) mild 17(37.0%) (Moderate 15(32.6 %) sever 2(4.3%) participants. in the z track technique group .no swelling 38 (82.6%) mild 8(17.4 %).

Discussion

The present study was conducted to examine the impact of the conventional intramuscular injection method and the Z-track method on pain intensity among hospitalized adult patients receiving intramuscular injections. To achieve the objectives of the study, two instruments were used for data collection: one to assess socio-demographic and clinical characteristics, and the other a standardized pain assessment tool. The study included a total of 92 adult patients who received intramuscular antibiotic injections. Of these, 46 participants were allocated to the conventional intramuscular injection group, while the remaining 46 participants received injections using the Z-track method. The study was carried out at Peoples Medical College Hospital. The finding of present study showed that age of participant ranged between 30 to 60 years, there was no statistically significant different between the conventional intramuscular injection and z track technique group in term of age categories ($p=0.585$). For comparison Heshmatifar et al (2022) who examined adult patient aged 25 to 60 years and reported mean age of (45.12 ± 7.80) in adult patient receiving intramuscular injection.²⁰ In the present study, no statistically significant difference was found between the conventional and z track technique group regarding pervious IM injection experience (conventional 63 % and ZTT 86% $p_0.521$). Similarly finding reported by saji et al (2024) reported that the ZTT was associated

with significantly lower pain perception compared with the standard method in orthopedics patients that procedure pain outcome are more strongly related to the technique used than to participants prior injection history.²¹ In the present study, the distribution of medication administered (dicolofence ,antibiotics and other drug) was similar between the conventional and z track group with no statistically significant difference($P=0.924$), In comparison Iliopoulos et al (2023) found that affixed dose IM combination of diclofenac and thicolchicoside produced significantly greater pain reduction than diclofenac immunotherapy at both 1 hour ($p<0,01$)and 3 hour ($p<0,01$) post injection ,demonstrating that variation in medication can result in different clinical outcome.²²In the present study the mean pain score were consistently lower in the ZTT group compared with conventional group had a mean pain score of mean \pm . SD (6.065 ± 1.200) than in z track group (4.587 ± 1.127) , $p=0.027$) . these finding are consistent with pervious research Kareem and Ajil (2025) found that neonate who receiving vitamin K injection by the ZTT experienced significantly lower pain score (3.28 ± 1.08) than those who received injection by the standard method (4.53 ± 1.26) ($p<.001$).²³In the present study, that group (84.7%) compared to the Z-track technique group (16.1%), similarly, medication group (14%). these results align with Yilmaz et al(2016)who reported that mean drug leakage measured in millimeter was significantly lower in the ZTT group (6.93 ± 4.62) than in the conventional group (10.03 ± 3.69) , $p < .05$) the ZTT Method reduces injection site leakage and improves procedural outcome.²⁴The present study Hematoma was observed in (75.0%) conventional IM group, (25.0%) of the Z-track group developed

hematoma ($p < 0.001$). These results comparable with Davido et al (2024), that the injection-site complications include hematoma were extremely rare 0.02% in a large hospitalized population receiving IM injection although their study did not directly compare injection technique.²⁵ The present study most participants experienced mild to severe bruising (47.8% mild, 39.1% moderate, 4.3% severe). In the Z-track group, 87.0% had no bruising and 13.0% had mild bruising. These findings align with Buldak & Çınar (2024), who reported significantly lower bruising after subcutaneous injections with intervention (11.5% vs. 38.5%, $p = .021$).²⁶ The present study Z-track technique resulted in lower incidence injection site redness 91.3% no redness compared with conventional IM injection method (34.8%) no redness.²⁷ These findings align with Babu et al. (2022), who reported that ZTT significantly reduced post injection gluteal inflammation compared to the standard technique this supports that ZTT minimizes local tissue irritation explaining the redness observed in your study.²⁸ The present study showed that the z track technique significantly reduced injection site swelling z track group had 82.6% with no swelling and 17.4% with mild swelling with no moderate or severe cases.²⁹ These results comparable with Sasireka and Bhubaneswar (2025) who reported that optimize injection technique pressure shot blocker significantly reduced post injection swelling in children compared with procedure ($p < .001$).³⁰

Conclusion: This study concluded that the Z-track technique is better and safe method for administration of Intramuscular injection compared to the conventional technique, it has minimal risk for drug leakage and other related complications. Furthermore, patient who received injection using the Z-track technique reported less pain more comfort. Moreover, Z-track technique should improve patient care and promote safer nursing practice.

Recommendation: The Z-track technique should be regularly practiced for intramuscular injection to reduce pain and other complications. Nurse should receive proper training and supervision to correctly perform the Z-track technique.

Moreover, Nursing education program should be conducted teaching and practice of technique Z-track technique. Further research should be carried out on larger population to support these findings.

Funding: self.

Conflict of Interest: There is no any conflict of interested among authors.

REFERENCE:

1. Heshmatifar, N. *et al.* A New Approach on the pain management of intramuscular injection: A Triple-Blind Randomized Clinical Trial. *Pain Manag. Nurs.* 23, 353–358 (2022). DOI: 10.1016/j.pmn.2021.01.010
2. Babu, J. J., Venkadalakshmi, V., Chopra, S. & Dhandapani, M. Z-track technique reduces pain at the injection site, drug leakage, post-injection gluteal inflammation in Pritchard regimen for severe pre-eclamptic patients: findings from a randomized controlled trial. *Int. J. Res. Med. Sci.* 10, 2190 (2022). doi.org/10.18203/2320-6012.ijrms20222522
3. Barış Eren, N. Evaluation of the effect of Z-track technique training on emergency nurses: A single-group pretest–posttest study. *Int. Emerg. Nurs.* 83, 101683 (2025). DOI: 10.1016/j.ienj.2025.101683
4. Ordu, Y., Polat, H. T. & Küçükceran, K. Effects of cold needle and ShotBlocker applied in the emergency department on pain and satisfaction in intramuscular injection pain: A randomized controlled trial. *Australas. Emerg. Care* (2025) doi:10.1016/J.AUEC.2025.02.001.
5. Yildiz, G. N. & Çiftçi, B. Deltoid muscle intramuscular injection methods examining pain comfort satisfaction and fear in ShotBlocker helper skin tap and standard techniques. *BMC Nurs.* 24, (2025). DOI: 10.1016/j.ienj.2025.101683

6. Baysal, E., Karakuş Selçuk, A. & Kışlali Taş, Ş. The Effect of Helfer Skin Tap Technique on Pain Reduction and Hemodynamic Parameters During Tetanus Injection in Pregnant Women. *Celal Bayar Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilim. Enstitüsü Derg.* 11, 462-473 (2024). DOI:10.34087/cbusbed.1502612
7. Ayinde, O., Hayward, R. S. & Ross, J. D. C. The effect of intramuscular injection technique on injection associated pain; a systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One* 16, e0250883 (2021). DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0250883
8. Herraiz-Adillo, Á., Martínez-Vizcaíno, V. & Pozuelo-Carrascosa, D. P. Aspiration before intramuscular vaccines injection, should the debate continue? *Enfermería Clínica (English Ed.)* 32, 65-66 (2022). doi: 10.1016/j.enfcl.2021.10.002
9. Leleu, A. et al. Symptom related to Essure® and evolution after removal: Outcomes of retrospective cohort. *J. Gynecol. Obstet. Hum. Reprod.* 50, (2021). DOI: 10.1016/j.jogoh.2020.101836
10. Güven, Ş. D. & Çakırer Çalbayram, N. The effect of Helfer skin tap technique on hepatitis B vaccine intramuscular injection pain in neonates: A randomized controlled trial. *Explore* 19, 238-242 (2023). DOI: 10.1016/j.explore.2022.09.001
11. Sari, D., Onder, H. E., Taskiran, N., Yardimci, F. & Tas, S. K. Effects of Buzzy® and ShotBlocker® on Pain and Anxiety During Immunization in Children: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Pain Manag. Nurs.* 26, e325-e331 (2025). DOI: 10.1016/j.pmn.2024.12.023
12. Karabey, T. & Karagözoğlu, Ş. The effect of new device on pain and comfort levels in individuals undergoing peripheral intravenous cannula insertion. *J. Vasc. Access* 25, 432-438 (2024). DOI: 10.1177/11297298221113685
13. Karabey, T. & Karagözoğlu, Ş. The Effect of Helfer Skin Tap Technique and ShotBlocker Application on Pain in Deltoid Muscle Injection. *Clin. Exp. Heal. Sci.* 11, 721-726 (2021). doi.org/10.33808/clinexphealthsci.861801
14. Öz, G. Ö. & Ordu, Y. The effects of web based education and Kahoot usage in evaluation of the knowledge and skills regarding intramuscular injection among nursing students. *Nurse Educ. Today* 103, (2021). DOI: 10.1016/j.nedt.2021.104910
15. Saji, J., Margaret, N. C. & Evency, A. R. Effectiveness of Z Track Technique Versus Standard Technique on Pain Perception During Intramuscular Injection among Patients Underwent Orthopaedic Surgery. *Res. Rev. Int. J. Multidiscip.* 9, 235-250 (2024). DOI:10.31305/rrijm.2024.v09.n05.029
16. Nakajima, Y. et al. Anatomically safe sites for intramuscular injections: a cross-sectional study on young adults and cadavers with a focus on the thigh. *Hum. Vaccines Immunother.* 16, 189-196 (2020). DOI: 10.1080/21645515.2019.1646576
17. Barış Eren, N. Evaluation of the effect of Z-track technique training on emergency nurses: A single-group pretest-posttest study. *Int. Emerg. Nurs.* 83, 101683 (2025). DOI: 10.1016/j.ienj.2025.101683
18. Enjeksiyon Uygulamalarında Kullanılan, İ., Tekniği, Z., Hemşirelerin Engelleri, K. & Baş, Y. D. Which is Used in Intramuscular Injections Applications Akd Hemşirelik D 2023. 2, 1-9. https://doi.org/10.59398/ahd.1123694
19. Barış Eren, N. et al. Determination of Nurses' Knowledge Levels on Using the Z-Track Technique in Intramuscular Injection Application. *Istanbul Gelisim Univ. J. Heal. Sci.* 24, 1222-1233 (2024). DOI:10.38079/igusabder.1508825

20. Geiger, M. K. *et al.* Performance of Early Fetal Echocardiography: An Expert Statement from the Fetal Heart Society. *J. Am. Soc. Echocardiogr.* (2025) doi:10.1016/j.echo.2025.09.020.
21. Quiñones-Rivera, J. N. *et al.* Outcomes after cerclage and preterm prelabor rupture of membranes: data from the international collaborative for cerclage longitudinal evaluation and research (IC-CLEAR). *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol. MFM* 7, (2025).
22. Sblendorio, E. Frontiers of Nursing Review Intramuscular vaccine administrations including the adoption of 'Zeta-track technique' & 'without aspiration slow injection technique' (ZTT & WASiT): a prospective review. *Front. Nurs.* • 10, 2023 (2023). DOI; 10.2478/fon-2023-0003
23. Inangil D, Şendir M. Effectiveness of mechano-analgesia and cold application on ecchymosis, pain, and patient satisfaction associated with subcutaneous heparin injection. *J Vasc Nurs.* 2020 Jun;38(2):76-82. doi: 10.1016/j.jvn.2020.02.002).
24. Umberger, W. Priorities in Complementary and Alternative Medicine Research for Pain Management: Advancing the State of the Science. *Pain Manag. Nurs.* 23, 249–250 (2022). DOI: 10.1016/j.pmn.2022.04.001
25. Geisler, A., Zachodnik, J., Nersesjan, M., Persson, E. & Mathiesen, O. Postoperative Pain Management and Patient Evaluations After Five Different Surgical Procedures. A Prospective Cohort Study. *Pain Manag. Nurs.* 23, 791–799 (2022). DOI: 10.1016/j.pmn.2022.06.006
26. Alan, N. & Khorshid, L. Evaluation of Efficacy of Valsalva Maneuver During Peripheral Intravenous Cannulation on Pain. *Pain Manag. Nurs.* 23, 220–224 (2022). DOI: 10.1016/j.pmn.2021.01.013
27. Taddio A, Wong H, Welkovich B, Ilersich AL, Cole M, Goldbach M, Ipp M. A randomized trial of the effect of vaccine injection speed on acute pain in infants. *Vaccine.* 2016 Sep 7;34(39):4672-4677. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2016.08.023.
28. Ausin-Crespo MD, Martín-de Castro E, Roldán-Cuartero J, de la Beldad-Diez ML, Salcedo-Gámez MÁ, Tong H. Capsaicin 8% Dermal Patch for Neuropathic Pain in a Pain Unit. *Pain Manag Nurs.* 2022 Aug;23(4):452-457. doi: 10.1016/j.pmn.2021.12.005. Epub 2022 Feb 6. PMID: 35135709.
29. Sarman, A. & Tuncay, S. Soothing venipuncture: Bubble blowing and ball squeezing in reducing anxiety, fear, and pain in children. *J. Child Adolesc. Psychiatr. Nurs.* 37, (2024). DOI: 10.1111/jcap.12478
30. Kışlalı Taş, Ş., Sari, D. & Taşkiran, N. Reducing Vaccination Pain in Infants: A Randomized Controlled Trial on the Effects of ShotBlocker and Manual Pressure. *Clin. Pediatr. (Phila).* (2025) doi:10.1177/00099228251387875.